

EAA 2020

VIRTUAL

24-30 August

#Networking

**26th EAA
Annual Meeting
Scientific Programme**

26th Annual Meeting of the European Association of Archaeologists - Scientific Programme

Names, titles and affiliations are reproduced as submitted by the session organisers and/or authors. Language and wording of titles and abstracts were not revised.

Technical editing: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

Design and layout: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

Photo: © Kateřina Kleinová

European Association of Archaeologists

Prague, August 2020

© European Association of Archaeologists, 2020

435 THE CLIMATE IMPACT ON EUROPEAN NEOLITHIC SOCIETIES DURING THE 8.2-KY BP EVENTS NEAR RIVER BASINS AND LAKES SHORES

Date: Saturday 29 August

Time: 16:00 - 18:00 CEST

Theme: 4. Waterscapes: archaeology and heritage of fresh waters

Format: Regular session

Organisers: Andriiovych, Marta (Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Demchenko, Olha (Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University; Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Hinz, Martin (Institute for Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern)

ABSTRACTS

- 16:00 **THE CLIMATIC IMPACT ON THE NEOLITHIZATION OF THE NORTHERN VOLGA RIVER BASIN**
Vybornov, Alexander (Samara State University of Social Sciences and Education) - Kulkova, Marianna (Herzen State University of Russia)
- 16:15 **GYRZHEVE - A COMPLEX ARCHAEOLOGICAL SEQUENCE IN SOUTH-WESTERN UKRAINE ENCOMPASSING THE 8200 CALBP EVENT**
Lishchyna, Kseniia (Odessa I. I. Mechnikov National University)
- 16:30 **RAPID CLIMATIC EVENTS AND SOCIAL DYNAMICS (8200-4000 CALBP)**
Kiosak, Dmytro (I.I. Mechnikov Odessa National University) - Ivanova, Svitlana (Institute of Archaeology National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine)
- 16:45 **MIGRATION OR JUST A «FASHION TREND»? ECOLOGICAL PRECONDITIONS AND PENETRATION PATHS OF IMPRESSO POTTERY INTO THE NORTHERN PONTIC REGION**
Demchenko, Olha (Odessa Ilya.I. Mechnikov National University; University of Bern)
- 17:00 **THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE NEOLITHIC SOCIAL GROUPS WITH MARIUPOL TYPE CEMETERIES AFTER EVENT 8.2 KY. BP**
Andriiovych, Marta - Hafner, Albert (Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Shydlovskiy, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Center for Paleoethnological Research)
- 17:15 **POPULATION DYNAMICS OF THE KYIV DNEPER REGION AT THE BORDER OF PLEISTOCENE - HOLOCENE**
Shydlovskiy, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv; Center for Paleoethnological Research) - Sorokun, Andrii (Institute of Archaeology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine; Bila Tserkva Local History Museum)
- 17:30 **DISCUSSION SLOT**

EAA 2020

VIRTUAL

24-30 August

#Networking

26th EAA Virtual Annual Meeting

Abstract Book

www.e-a-a.org/ea2020virtual
[#ea2020virtual](https://twitter.com/ea2020virtual)

ORGANISER

HOW TO READ THE ABSTRACT BOOK

The Abstract Book is ordered by session numbers which were allocated during the session submission (i.e., the number sequence is discontinuous).

Author's affiliation is stated in brackets following the author's name; where authors share the same affiliation, it is only stated once.

Index of Authors includes all session organisers and only the main authors of contributions.

Please note that names, titles and affiliations are reproduced as submitted by the session organisers and/or authors. Language and wording of titles and abstracts are not revised.

26th EAA Virtual Annual Meeting - Abstract Book

Technical editing: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

Design and layout: Kateřina Kleinová (EAA)

ISBN: 978-80-907270-7-6

European Association of Archaeologists

Prague, August 2020

© European Association of Archaeologists, 2020

426	MEDIEVAL URBAN PARISH-CHURCHES: AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE.....	427
428	MEDIEVAL MINING DISTRICT. A EUROPEAN LANDSCAPE PERSPECTIVE.....	429
435	THE CLIMATE IMPACT ON EUROPEAN NEOLITHIC SOCIETIES DURING THE 8.2-KY BP EVENTS NEAR RIVER BASINS AND LAKES SHORES.....	433
436	NOW YOU CAN'T SEE ME! SEARCHING FOR RESILIENCE AS AN ARCHAEOLOGICALLY OBSERVABLE PHENOMENON.....	435
438	ARCHAEOLOGY AND ITS POLITICAL USES: HISTORICAL, HISTORIOGRAPHIC AND IDEOLOGICAL DISCOURSES.....	438
441	WEAVING MOBILITY. MOVEMENT OF PEOPLE, TOOLS, AND TECHNIQUES IN THE TEXTILE ARCHAEOLOGY OF THE ANCIENT MEDITERRANEAN.....	441
444	14C: THE CLOCK READING THE PAST AND PRESENT OF THE HUMANKIND.....	444
445	MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES TO IDENTIFY AND PRESERVE FIBRES AND TEXTILE PRODUCTS IN THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL FIELD ...	446
448	JUST A DEMONSTRATION OF POWER? THE SETTING OF STRONGHOLDS WITHIN THEIR LANDSCAPE [COMFORT].....	450
454	ARCHAEOLOGY AND INFRASTRUCTURE: FUTURE NETWORKS, CONTEMPORARY COLLABORATIONS AND PAST LANDSCAPES.....	453
455	KNAPP, KNAPP - WHO'S THERE? LITHICS AND THEIR INTERPRETATIONAL ATTRIBUTES.....	455
457	FROM NOVICES TO EXPERTS: DEVELOPMENT AND TRANSMISSION OF TECHNICAL KNOWLEDGE IN PREHISTORY.....	459
458	INTERDISCIPLINARITY IN THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH OF RELIGIOUS PHENOMENA.....	462
462	THE MONGOL INVASION OF CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE: ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND HISTORICAL INTERPRETATIONS.....	466
464	TRAUM - TRACING REALITY IN ARCHAEOLOGY USING MACHINE LEARNING.....	468
465	NETWORKING: BRINGING SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO SENSORY ARCHAEOLOGY.....	470
468	PRE-CHRISTIAN BELIEFS OF CENTRAL AND NORTHERN EUROPE. INTERDISCIPLINARY INVESTIGATIONS.....	471
470	NON-INVASIVE REGIONAL SURVEY STRATEGIES: DISCUSSING THE METHODOLOGICAL GOLDEN MEAN.....	474
472	UTILISING ARCHIVES FOR CURRENT RESEARCH PURPOSE, THE DIFFICULTIES IN FORWARD COMPATIBILITY, STORAGE, ACCURACY AND ACCESS AND THE PROBLEMS ASSOCIATED.....	479
473	CARPATHIAN BASIN AND ITS BORDERS IN TIME OF WARS BETWEEN FALL OF CONSTANTINOPLE AND THE END OF WORLD WAR 2	480
474	THE BIOARCHAEOLOGY OF LETHAL VIOLENCE AND OTHER NOT-SO-ULTIMATE INTERACTIONS: EXPLORING THE INTERFACE BETWEEN TRAUMA AND TAPHONOMY.....	483
477	NOVEL CROSS-DISCIPLINARY APPROACHES IN BIOARCHAEOLOGY.....	488
478	THE RISE OF THE RELIGIOUS LANDSCAPE IN CARPATHIAN BASIN: THE ARCHAEOLOGY OF ROUND SHAPED CHURCHES AND THEIR EUROPEAN CONTEXT.....	491
479	CONSTRUCTIVE CONSERVATION: MAKING MONUMENTS USEFUL.....	493
480	HOW TO PROMOTE INTER- AND TRANSDISCIPLINARITY IN MEDITERRANEAN ARCHAEOLOGY?.....	495
481	CROSS-DISCIPLINARY APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL WOODCRAFTS AND OTHER PLANT-BASED IMPLEMENTS AND STRUCTURES [ARCHAEOLOGY OF WILD PLANTS].....	497
482	NEW AND INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES IN THE RESEARCH OF PREHISTORIC WATERBORNE COMMUNICATION AND EXCHANGE ALONG EUROPEAN RIVERS, LAKES AND COASTAL WATERS [PAM].....	499
483	MEDIEVAL STONE MONUMENTS [SEAC].....	501
485	THE ARCHAEOLOGY OF RECOVERY: THE AFTERMATH OF WAR.....	503
487	MEGALITHS ON THE EDGE: THE PLACE OF CULTURAL TRANSFORMATION.....	506
488	'...IN WITH THE NEW!' UP AND COMING ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH IN MEDIEVAL EUROPE IN 2020.....	509
489	25 YEARS AFTER: PAST AND FUTURE OF SOME COMMON PLACES IN ARCHAEOLOGY [EAA].....	511
490	STANDARDISING ARCHAEOLOGISTS' PROFESSIONAL SKILLS IN EUROPE: NATIONAL DIFFERENCES, TRANSNATIONAL SIMILARITIES [DISCO, PAA].....	513
501	GENERAL SESSION - LANDSCAPES IN FLUX.....	514
502	GENERAL SESSION - LITHICS IN DIFFERENT CONTEXT.....	516
503	GENERAL SESSION - HUMAN-ANIMAL RELATIONSHIPS.....	520
504	GENERAL SESSION - HERITAGE IN FOCUS.....	523
505	GENERAL SESSION - WATERSCAPES.....	526
506	GENERAL SESSION - MICROARCHAEOLOGY OF PAST BODIES.....	529
507	GENERAL SESSION - LIMES, BORDERS, MARGINAL ZONES.....	532
508	GENERAL SESSION - NEOLITHIC WORLD.....	535
509	GENERAL SESSION - EURASIAN NOMADS.....	538

Theme: 4. Waterscapes: archaeology and heritage of fresh waters

Organisers: Andriiovych, Marta (Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Demchenko, Olha (Odessa I.I. Mechnikov National University; Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Hinz, Martin (Institute for Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern)

Format: Regular session

The transition from the Early to the Middle Neolithic coincides with the 8.2-ky BP event in some areas of Europe. This climatological event, which lasted between 150 to 400 years, has received considerable interest in various scientific fields, from ecologists, climatologists and geologists to archaeologists and dendrochronologists, due to the major changes it has triggered worldwide.

The 8.2-ky BP event initiated with a rapid decline in the average temperature, which could have a major influence on the Neolithic populations as a whole: from changes in the local cultural, social and economic practices to waves of migration. According to the latest results, there might be a link between climatic and cultural changes during the Early and Middle Neolithic in Europe and the Near East. In addition to the cooling effect, the significant rise in sea levels has mainly affected river systems. The communities living in these areas were therefore under particular adaptation pressure. Also, during that time there is evidence of migration waves of Early Neolithic communities in eastern Europe and at the Mediterranean coasts. The 8.2-ky BP effects might be visible in Neolithic cultures of the Cyprus, Greece, Northern Macedonia, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Poland, Spain territories.

The paleoclimate changes could have reversed the neolithization of Europe, but they triggered innovation and adaptation processes. This is supported by the fact that around the transition from the 6th to 5th millennium BCE several communities started to produce ceramics. They also coincided with the rapid increase in water level in the Mediterranean and Black Seas and generally increased aridity.

For this session, we invite presentations dealing with the specific situation of the waterfront community in the face of the changed climatic situation and possible positive or negative consequences on settlement as well as on the innovative potential.

ABSTRACTS

5 THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE NEOLITHIC SOCIAL GROUPS WITH MARIUPOL TYPE CEMETERIES AFTER EVENT 8.2 KY. BP

Abstract author(s): Andriiovych, Marta (Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Hafner, Albert (Institute of Archaeological Sciences, University of Bern) - Shydlovskiy, Pavlo (Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine; Center for Paleoethnological Research, Ukraine)

Abstract format: Oral

Human groups generally react sensitively to all changes that affect their everyday life.

During the 160-400 year cooling phase about 8'200 years ago, several major environmental changes took place: the increase of water in the ocean and seas; the cooling of the average temperature by $-3.3 \pm 1.1^{\circ}\text{C}$; the aridification of the North Africa and the Middle East, to name only the most significant effects. Such changes may have had an impact on the Neolithic populations of the Middle East and Europe.

On the territory of today's Ukraine, the 8.2 ky BP event coincides with the transition from the Mesolithic and early Neolithic way of life. The late Mesolithic cultures of Donetsk and Kukrek became important transitional groups in the Early Neolithic. And at the same time, Early Neolithic groups already formed, which are called Bug-Dniester, Surska, and Azov-Dnieper cultures. Simultaneously with the cooling, these societies underwent profound changes, which may have been caused by the settlement of new groups in the region. One of the "characteristics" of these new cultural groups is the production of ceramic objects such as pottery.